

MAXWELL'S EQUATIONS AND QUANTUM ENTANGLEMENT FROM THE TOPOLOGY OF SPACETIME

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ABSTRACT. Internal spacetime was recently introduced with the aim of modeling quantum phenomena using metrics that are degenerate along particle worldlines. We show that cohomology sees these degenerate worldlines as holes in spacetime, and from this Maxwell's equations naturally appear. We also derive Malus's law and the quantum correlations of entangled pairs of electrons and photons from the spacetime topology. In particular, electromagnetism and spin entanglement have the same topological origin. Moreover, the spacelike correlations central to entanglement result from the new source of time dilation inherent in the geometry.

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1. INTRODUCTION: INTERNAL SPACETIME

Internal spacetime geometry, recently proposed in [B5] to address the quantum measurement problem, modifies general relativity by taking the spacetime metric to be degenerate along the worldlines of fundamental particles. The resulting degenerate geometry exhibits interesting similarities to the standard model [B1, B2, B3].

In this paper we show how this degenerate geometry has a natural topology where certain submanifolds are effectively removed, or carved out, from a spacetime manifold. The electromagnetic 2-form $F = dA$ then appears directly from this topology; in particular, there is no need to add an auxiliary principle $U(1)$ -bundle structure to spacetime. This same topology further implies that the preparation and measurement of an entangled pair of particles are simultaneous events, and this property allows for measurement independence despite the spacelike correlations of the entangled pair.

Key words and phrases. Spacetime geometry, degenerate spacetime metrics, Maxwell's equations, quantum entanglement, de Rham cohomology.

We briefly summarize internal spacetime geometry. Let $(\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}_{ab})$ be a Lorentzian manifold, called *external spacetime*. Consider a locally finite collection of particles in \tilde{M} , called *pointons*, with timelike or null worldlines $\beta \subset \tilde{M}$. We define *internal spacetime* M , or simply *spacetime*, to be the geometry obtained by declaring time to be stationary along each pointon worldline β .¹

Explicitly, a metric for M at a point $p \in \tilde{M}$ is obtained from the external metric \tilde{g}_{ab} by projecting out the unit tangent vectors $v \in \tilde{M}_p$ to each $\beta \subset \tilde{M}$ that meets p :

$$h_{ab} := [v_1]_{ac}[v_2]^c \cdots [v_n]^e{}_b : \tilde{M}_p \otimes \tilde{M}_p \rightarrow \mathbb{R},$$

where, by [B5, Lemma 2.3] with metric signature $(-+++)$,

$$(1) \quad [v]_{ab} := \begin{cases} \tilde{g}_{ab} + v_a v_b & \text{if } v \text{ is timelike,} \\ \tilde{g}_{ab} + v_a v'_b + v_b v'_a, & \text{if } v \text{ is null, for some null } v' \text{ with } v^a v'_a = -1. \end{cases}$$

A continuous degenerate metric g_{ab} may then be constructed from h_{ab} [B2, §3], but we shall only use h_{ab} here. Indices continue to be raised and lowered (that is, the tangent and cotangent spaces of \tilde{M} are identified) using the external metric \tilde{g}_{ab} .

The *tangent space* of M at $p \in \tilde{M}$ is the subspace of \tilde{M}_p given by the image $M_p := \text{im } h_a{}^b \subset \tilde{M}_p$ (see Definition 2.7). The dimension of M_p is thus the rank of h_{ab} at p . Notably, the tangent space dimension is not constant over \tilde{M} .

By Hodge duality, the vanishing subspace $\ker h_a{}^b$ orthogonal to M_p in \tilde{M}_p acquires a free choice of orientation $o \in \{\pm 1\}$ (Section 2.1). If a timelike resp. spacelike direction vanishes, then o is identified with electric resp. color charge; and if two spacelike directions vanish, then o is identified with spin, up or down, in the one surviving spatial direction of M_p .

The latter case occurs when two pointons meet at a point $p \in \tilde{M}$: the orientation o specifies a unique spacelike unit vector $s \in M_p$, which we call a *spin vector*.² This vector is then Fermi transported along the pointon's worldline. Denote by $h_p(s) := h_a{}^b s^a$ the projection of s onto M_p , and by $\hat{h}_p(s) := h_p(s)/|h_p(s)|$ its normalization if nonzero, and 0 otherwise. For two spacelike vectors $u_1, u_2 \in \tilde{M}_p$, we will often write $u_1 \cdot u_2 := h_{ab} u_1^a u_2^b = h(u_1, u_2)$ for their scalar product in M_p .

- (i) When s enters a smaller dimensional tangent space M_p , s is projected onto it by $\hat{h}_p : \tilde{M}_p \rightarrow M_p$, and this corresponds to a measurement of spin at p .

¹We call the particles ‘pointons’ because their worldlines are single 1-dimensional points in M in the sense of nonnoetherian algebraic geometry; see [B4].

²Consider a pointon with timelike worldline $\beta \subset \tilde{M}$ and 4-velocity $v \in \tilde{M}_{\beta(t)}$. Let $e_0 = v, e_1, e_2, e_3$ be an orthonormal tetrad Fermi transported along β . Then the pointon's spin vector $s \in S^2 \subset M_{\beta(t)}$ is mapped to the spin Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} \cong \mathbb{C}^2$ with e_3 basis $|\uparrow\rangle, |\downarrow\rangle$ by

$$s = \sin \vartheta \cos \varphi e_1 + \sin \vartheta \sin \varphi e_2 + \cos \vartheta e_3 \quad \mapsto \quad |s\rangle = \cos \frac{\vartheta}{2} |\uparrow\rangle + e^{i\varphi} \sin \frac{\vartheta}{2} |\downarrow\rangle.$$

- (ii) When s exits a smaller dimensional tangent space M_p , the time-reversal of (i) occurs: a section s' of the normalized projection $\hat{h}_p : \tilde{M}_p \rightarrow M_p$ is chosen such that $\hat{h}_p(s') = s$, with probability density

$$(2) \quad \rho(s' | s) \propto h_{ab} s^a s'^b = s \cdot s'.$$

If the tangent space M_q at a point $q \in \tilde{M}$ is 1-dimensional, then *the outcome of a measurement of spin s in the direction of a unit vector $u \in M_q$ at q is given by*

$$(3) \quad \bar{u}(s) := \mathbf{1}(u \cdot s) - \mathbf{1}(-u \cdot s) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } u \cdot s > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } u \cdot s = 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } u \cdot s < 0 \end{cases}$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the Heaviside function: $\mathbf{1}(x) = 1$ if $x \geq 0$ and 0 otherwise. Furthermore, in [KS] Kochen and Specker showed that the probability density (2) exactly reproduces the Born rule for spin; our model is thus a spacetime realization of their model. In [B5, §6], we extended their result to the Born rule for polarization using two spin vectors. Thus, pointons are spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ fermions, and bound pairs of pointons are spin-1 bosons.

It was shown in [B5, Theorem 5.1] that pointons with null geodesic worldlines are necessarily bound in pairs of opposite electric charge. This leads to the natural identification of electrons, positrons, and photons given in Figure 1.

We briefly outline our main results. To note, Sections 3 and 4 do not assume familiarity with differential topology; readers primarily interested in quantum entanglement may wish to start with Section 3.

In Section 2 we introduce a natural topology on internal spacetime M , and show that M is a T_1 non-Hausdorff space. Since M is not Hausdorff, de Rham's theorem does not hold: singular cohomology and de Rham cohomology differ for M . Suppose \tilde{M} is homeomorphic to Minkowski space $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$, and denote by \mathcal{D} the set of worldvolumes $\beta \subset \tilde{M}$ that are degenerate in M . We show that (Theorem 2.8)

$$H_{\text{dR}}^n(M) \cong H_{\text{dR}}^n(\tilde{M} \setminus \cup_{\beta \in \mathcal{D}} \beta).$$

The electromagnetic field $\star F = E_{ab} - B_a \wedge dt$ is then a canonical generator of $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$ (Definition 2.10). *Thus, the electromagnetic field is a topological property of spacetime M itself.* We further show that on M , Maxwell's equations are equivalent to the massless Dirac equation.

In Section 3 we present the conditional probabilities for spin and polarization (Lemma 3.2). We also show how the degenerate metric h gives rise to the polarization type of a photon: linear, circular, or elliptical.

In Section 4 we introduce a geometric model of quantum entanglement for the Bell states (Definition 4.2). We find that, although measurement independence is violated in \tilde{M} , it is not violated in spacetime M itself (Proposition 4.3). Moreover,

FIGURE 1. Left: An internal spacetime model of electrons and photons. Right: (i) A spacetime diagram of two photons entangled in a Bell state, drawn in green and orange. (ii) Similarly for electrons.

given detector settings $a, b \in S^2$, our model yields expectation values that agree with quantum theory (Theorems 4.4 and 4.8),

$$\pm \langle \bar{a} \bar{b} \rangle_{\pm} := \int_{S^n} \rho(s|P) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(s) ds = \begin{cases} a \cdot b = \cos \theta & \text{for electrons} \\ \cos(2\theta) & \text{for photons} \end{cases}$$

where P is the preparation procedure, and θ is the angle between (the Fermi transports of) a and b . We further show that a photon passing through two linear polarizers, in the directions $u_1, u_2 \in S^1$, satisfies Malus's law (Theorem 4.7),

$$P(u_2 | u_1) = (u_1 \cdot u_2)^2.$$

Finally, we show that our model naturally extends to (delayed choice) entanglement swapping.

Degenerate spacetime metrics have also appeared in other contexts in the literature, such as in the regularization of spacetime singularities [Ba, K1, K2, K3, KW], loop quantum gravity [LW], and extensions of general relativity [GB].

Notation: Tensors labeled with upper and lower indices a, b, \dots represent covector and vector slots respectively in Penrose's abstract index notation (so $v^a \in V$ and $v_a \in V^*$), and tensors labeled with indices μ, ν, \dots denote components with respect to a coordinate basis. Unless stated otherwise, we will use natural units $\hbar = c = G = 1$ and the signature $(-, +, +, +)$.

2. MAXWELL'S EQUATIONS FROM SPACETIME TOPOLOGY

2.1. Preliminaries: Charge and spin from vanishing subspaces.

Definition 2.1. Given a set \mathcal{D} of degenerate worldvolumes in \tilde{M} , (*internal*) spacetime M is the image of the multivalued map $\phi : \tilde{M} \rightarrow M$ where

- ϕ is the identity on $\tilde{M} \setminus \cup_{\beta \in \mathcal{D}} \beta$; and
- the images $\phi(\beta), \phi(\beta')$ of distinct worldvolumes $\beta, \beta' \in \mathcal{D}$ are distinct single points of M .

Note that ϕ is m -valued at points where m degenerate worldvolumes intersect.

Throughout, we make the following standing assumptions:

- (i) If $\beta \in \mathcal{D}$ has initial (resp. final) point $\beta(t) \in \tilde{M}$, then there is a $\beta' \in \mathcal{D}$ with non-initial (resp. non-final) point $\beta'(t') = \beta(t)$.
- (ii) Each compact set of \tilde{M} meets at most a finite number of worldvolumes in \mathcal{D} .

Informally, assumption (i) says that we exclude pointal particle vacuum fluctuations.

A particle with a worldline β in \mathcal{D} is called a *pointon*. Consider a pointon with a timelike worldline β . The unit tangent vector $v \in \tilde{M}_{\beta(t)}$ to β , that is, the pointon's 4-velocity v , vanishes in spacetime M , and so must be replaced by a new object that is defined using only M . Just as a plane $u \cdot (x, y, z) = 0$ through the origin in \mathbb{R}^3 is uniquely specified by an orthogonal unit vector $\pm u \in \mathbb{R}^3$ up to a choice of sign, the pointon's 4-velocity is uniquely specified by its orthogonal complement, whence its Hodge dual, up to a choice of sign:

Definition 2.2. [B5, 3.1] The *internal velocity* of a pointal particle at $p \in \tilde{M}$ is the pseudovector

$$\check{v}^{a \cdots b} := o_{\ker h} \star \text{vol}(\ker h) \in \bigwedge^{\dim M_p} \tilde{M}_p,$$

where $\text{vol}(\ker h)$ is the volume element for the kernel of h at p , and $o_{\ker h} \in \{\pm 1\}$ is a free choice of orientation, independent of $o_{\tilde{M}}$.

For each vanishing subspace of $\tilde{M}_{\beta(t)}$, we thus obtain a free choice of orientation. We identify these orientations with charge or spin:

$$\text{vanishing subspace} \longleftrightarrow \text{choice of orientation} \longleftrightarrow \text{charge or spin}$$

These identifications are given in Table 1.

Notably, we define electric charge to a free choice of timelike orientation o_0 , and color charge $o_i, i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, to be the spatial version of electric charge o_0 [B1, B2]. In particular, there are three color charges because space is three dimensional. Choosing the unphysical orientation of \tilde{M} to be $o_{\tilde{M}} = 1$, we have $o_i = o_i o_{\tilde{M}} = o_{0jk}$. Thus, the color charge o_i arises from a worldvolume $\beta \in \mathcal{D}$ with vanishing tangent space spanned by e_0, e_j, e_k .

The simplest geometric models of the first generation particles that are able to reproduce the correct charges and approximate masses are given in Table 2; see

TABLE 1. Charge and spin from vanishing subspaces of spacetime tangent spaces [B3, B5]. We take the unphysical choice of orientation of \tilde{M} to be 1: $o_{\tilde{M}} = o_{0123} = o_0 o_1 o_2 o_3 = 1$.

vanishing subspace	free orientation	identification
e_0	$o_0 = o_{123}$	electric charge q
$e_0 \wedge e_2 \wedge e_3$	$o_1 = o_{023}$	color charge r^{o_1}
$e_0 \wedge e_3 \wedge e_1$	$o_2 = o_{013}$	color charge g^{o_2}
$e_0 \wedge e_1 \wedge e_2$	$o_3 = o_{012}$	color charge b^{o_3}
$e_2 \wedge e_3$	$o_{23} = o_{01}$	spin in the direction $o_{01}e_1$
$e_3 \wedge e_1$	$o_{13} = o_{02}$	spin in the direction $o_{02}e_2$
$e_1 \wedge e_2$	$o_{12} = o_{03}$	spin in the direction $o_{03}e_3$

TABLE 2. The degenerate worldvolumes $\beta \subset \tilde{M}$ of the first generation particles determined in [B2, §3], and the second de Rham cohomology groups $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$ each induces on $\tilde{M} \cong \mathbb{R}^{1,3}$.

particle	spatial slice of worldvolume β	$H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$
electron neutrino ν_e	$\longleftrightarrow \emptyset$ (a free spinor)	0
electron e	\longleftrightarrow a point (a <i>pointon</i>)	\mathbb{R}
up quark u	\longleftrightarrow a 2-sphere S^2 (a <i>pointal sphere</i>)	\mathbb{R}
down quark d	\longleftrightarrow a union of a point and S^2	$\mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbb{R}$

[B2, B3]. Specifically, an electron is modeled by a pointon, and the simplest spatial slice of a worldvolume with color charge is a sphere S^2 . All of the points on such a sphere $S^2 \subset \tilde{M}$ are identified, and therefore the sphere is a single point $\phi(S^2)$ in spacetime M . We call this geometric object a *pointal sphere*.

We take the electric charge of an (anti-)electron—that is, a pointon p —to be $q(p) = -o_0$, where the minus sign is inserted to agree with convention. The electric charges of the quarks are then obtained by setting $q(S^2) := \frac{2}{3}o_0$ for a pointal sphere S^2 :

$$\begin{aligned}
 e^\mp &= e^{-o_0} : & q_e &= q(p) = -o_0 \\
 u/\bar{u} &: & q_u &= q(S^2) = \frac{2}{3}o_0 \\
 d/\bar{d} &: & q_d &= q(S^2 \sqcup \{p\}) = q(S^2) + q(p) = \frac{2}{3}o_0 - o_0 = -\frac{1}{3}o_0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Given $q(S^2) = \frac{2}{3}o_0$, we are able to *derive* the electric charge of the down quark from our geometric model; however, the factor of $\frac{2}{3}$ in $q(S^2)$ warrants further justification.

2.2. The homology and de Rham cohomology of spacetime. A well-known mathematical coincidence is that the second de Rham cohomology group $H_{\text{dR}}^2(\mathbb{R}^4 \setminus \mathbb{R})$ is generated by a 2-form that is identical to the electromagnetic 2-form $\star F = E_{ab} - B_a \wedge dt$ of a single charged particle (e.g., [BT, p. 8], [N, §37.9]). In this section we show that, although Minkowski space $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ with a single pointon and $\mathbb{R}^4 \setminus \mathbb{R}$ are topologically and homologically quite different, they nevertheless share the same de Rham cohomology.

Definition 2.3. The topology of an internal spacetime $M = \phi(\tilde{M})$ has a basis defined by declaring the restriction $\phi|_{\tilde{M} \setminus \cup_{\beta \in \mathcal{D}} \beta} = \text{id}$ to be a topological embedding (i.e., a homeomorphism onto its image), and each singleton to be closed.

The restriction $\phi|_{\tilde{M} \setminus \cup_{\beta \in \mathcal{D}} \beta}$ is then both open and closed. The following shows that this property cannot be extended to ϕ itself.

Lemma 2.4. *If $\mathcal{D} \neq \emptyset$, then ϕ cannot be an open and closed map.*

Proof. Suppose $\beta \in \mathcal{D}$, and assume to the contrary that ϕ is open and closed. Let $B_1, B_2 \subset \tilde{M}$ be open balls that each contain a point of β , such that $B_1 \cap B_2 = \emptyset$. Then $\phi(B_1) \cap \phi(B_2) = \phi(\beta)$. Thus, $\phi(\beta)$ is open since ϕ is open. Whence its complement $\phi(\beta)^c$ is closed in M . Let $D \subset \tilde{M}$ be a closed disk that intersects β transversely. Then $\phi(D)$ is closed since ϕ is closed. Therefore $\phi(D) \cap \phi(\beta)^c$ is closed. But $\phi(D) \cap \phi(\beta)^c$ is homeomorphic to the unit disk in \mathbb{R}^2 with the origin removed, which is not closed. \square

Lemma 2.5. *Spacetime M is a T_1 space, but not Hausdorff if two degenerate worldvolumes intersect.*

Proof. M is a T_1 space since each singleton of M is a closed set. Suppose that there are distinct worldvolumes $\beta, \beta' \in \mathcal{D}$ with nonempty intersection, $\beta \cap \beta' \neq \emptyset$. Observe that there is only one open set in the topology basis that does not contain $\phi(\beta)$ but contains $\phi(\beta')$, namely, the complement of the singleton $\{\phi(\beta)\}$. However, $\{\phi(\beta_1)\}^c \cap \{\phi(\beta_2)\}^c \neq \emptyset$. Therefore M is not Hausdorff. \square

To determine the homology $H_n(M) := H_n(M; \mathbb{Z})$ of a spacetime M , we use singular homology (rather than, for example, simplicial homology) since M is not Hausdorff in general by Lemma 2.5.

Lemma 2.6. *Suppose \tilde{M} is homeomorphic to $\mathbb{R}^{1,3} \cong \mathbb{R}^4$, and contains a single pointal particle $\beta(t)$. Then the singular homology of M is*

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{for } \beta(t) \text{ an electron or neutrino:} & \text{for } \beta(t) \text{ an up quark or down quark:} \\ H_n(M) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{Z} & \text{if } n = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} & H_n(M) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{Z} & \text{if } n = 0 \text{ or } 3 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{array}$$

Proof. Recall the degenerate worldvolumes β of the first generation particles given in Table 2. If $\beta(t)$ is an electron or electron neutrino, then M is clearly contractible.

On the other hand, a quark is either a pointal sphere (an up quark), or the union of a pointon and pointal sphere (a down quark). In either case, since a pointal sphere $S^2 = \partial B^3$ in \tilde{M} is mapped to a single point $\phi(S^2)$ in M , the image $\phi(B^3)$ of the corresponding closed ball B^3 is a 3-sphere S^3 in M . Furthermore, $H_n(S^3) = \mathbb{Z}$ for $n \in \{0, 3\}$, and is trivial otherwise. Since $\mathcal{D} = \{\beta\}$, assumption (i) implies that β has no endpoints. Thus, $\beta = S^2 \times \mathbb{R}_t \subset \tilde{M} = \mathbb{R}^{1,3}$. It therefore follows that $H_n(M) \cong H_n(S^3)$ by a deformation retraction along the line \mathbb{R}_t . \square

The singular homology of a spacetime with multiple pointal particles (satisfying assumptions (i) and (ii)) can then be obtained using Lemma 2.6 together with a Mayer-Vietoris sequence.

Let N be a smooth manifold with differential n -forms $\Omega^n := \Omega^n(N) = \Gamma(\Lambda^n T^*N)$. Recall that the exterior derivative $d = d_n := dx^\mu \wedge \partial_\mu : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega^{n+1}$ is the flux density of an n -form through the boundary of an infinitesimal $(n+1)$ -cell.³ The holes in N are then counted by the de Rham cohomology groups

$$H_{\text{dR}}^n(N) := \ker d_n / \text{im } d_{n-1} = \{\text{closed } n\text{-forms}\} / \{\text{exact } n\text{-forms}\}.$$

Notably, de Rham's theorem states that $H_{\text{dR}}^n(N)$ is isomorphic to the singular cohomology group $H^n(N; \mathbb{R})$ by the pairing $H_n(N; \mathbb{R}) \times H_{\text{dR}}^n(N) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : (\Sigma, \omega) \mapsto \int_\Sigma \omega$. An internal spacetime M , however, is not a manifold (see [B5, §A1]), and generally not Hausdorff, and so de Rham's theorem is not applicable to M .

Recall that along a worldline β , a vector field u , which is orthogonal to the 4-velocity v of $\beta(\tau)$, is said to be Fermi transported if $\nabla u / d\tau = \lambda v$ for some function λ [F1, p. 73]; along geodesics, Fermi transport and parallel transport agree. Furthermore, *Fermi transport on \tilde{M} is parallel transport on M since $h_{\beta(\tau)}(v) = 0$* . To determine $H_{\text{dR}}^n(M)$ for an internal spacetime M , we introduce the following.

Definition 2.7. Let (M, h) be an internal spacetime. The *tangent bundle* of M is

$$TM := \bigcup_{p \in \tilde{M}} \{\phi(p)\} \times \text{im } h_p \xrightarrow{\pi} M,$$

where $\pi(\phi(p), v) = \phi(p)$. Note that $\text{im } h_p = \text{im } h_q$ whenever $\phi(p) = \phi(q)$, and π is multivalued whenever $\phi(p)$ is multivalued (that is, at interaction vertices in \tilde{M}). The *tangent space* at $p \in \tilde{M}$ is then the subspace $M_p := \text{im } h_p$ of \tilde{M}_p , with M_p and M_q identified by Fermi transport whenever $\phi(p) = \phi(q)$; we may thus write $M_{\phi(p)} := M_p$. Furthermore, if $\phi(p) = \{\phi(\beta_1), \dots, \phi(\beta_m)\}$ for some $\beta_i \in \mathcal{D}$, then

$$\{\phi(p)\} \times M_p = \{\phi(\beta_1), \dots, \phi(\beta_m)\} \times \bigcap_{i=1}^m M_{\phi(\beta_i)} \in TM.$$

³This follows from Stokes' theorem, $\int_{\partial V} \omega = \int_V d\omega$, where V is a compact submanifold with boundary ∂V . In \mathbb{R}^3 , d acts on 0-forms by the gradient, 1-forms by the curl, and 2-forms by the divergence.

Such an element is not in the image of any section $\sigma : M \rightarrow TM$ whenever $m \geq 2$. Finally, we call a section $\sigma : M \rightarrow TM$ *smooth* if it is smooth on the interior of each compact set in M .

Theorem 2.8. *Suppose \tilde{M} is homeomorphic to $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$. Then*

$$H_{\text{dR}}^n(M) \cong H_{\text{dR}}^n(\tilde{M} \setminus \cup_{\beta \in \mathcal{D}} \beta).$$

Proof. Let η be a smooth tensor field on M , and fix $\beta \in \mathcal{D}$. By Lemma 2.5, M is a T_1 space, and so the point $\phi(\beta)$ is closed in M .

If β has an endpoint $\beta(t)$ in \tilde{M} , then any open set in \tilde{M} that contains $\beta(t)$ must also contain the endpoint $\beta'(t) = \beta(t)$ of another $\beta' \in \mathcal{D}$, by assumption (i). Whence, any open set in M that contains $\phi(\beta)$ must also contain $\phi(\beta')$. Thus, $\phi(\beta)$ is not contained in the interior of any *compact* set of M , by assumptions (i) and (ii). It follows that, in regards to the smooth structure of η , the tangent space $M_{\phi(\beta)}$ is detached, or isolated, from the rest of the tangent bundle TM . Consequently, *to a smooth tensor field on M , the point $\phi(\beta)$ is effectively a hole in M .*

In particular, let $\omega \in \Omega^n(M)$ be a differential (whence smooth) n -form on M . Then the multilinear map

$$\omega_{\phi(\beta)} : \bigoplus_{i=1}^n M_{\phi(\beta)} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

is independent of $\omega_{\phi(p)}$ for points $p \in \tilde{M} \setminus \beta$. Therefore, since $\phi(\beta)$ is a single point, ω is exact on $\phi(\beta)$. \square

The de Rham groups $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$ for the first generation particles are given in Table 2. For the case of an electron, consider a single pointon worldline $\beta = (t, 0, 0, 0) : \mathbb{R}_t \rightarrow \tilde{M} = \mathbb{R}^{1,3}$. Then by Theorem 2.8,

$$H_{\text{dR}}^2(M) = H_{\text{dR}}^2(\mathbb{R}^{1,3} \setminus \mathbb{R}_t) \cong \mathbb{R}.$$

For any $q \neq 0$, this group is generated by (e.g., [BT, p. 8])

$$\begin{aligned} \star F &= -\frac{q}{4\pi r^2} \star dr \wedge dt = \frac{q}{4\pi r^3} (x dy \wedge dz + y dz \wedge dx + z dx \wedge dy) \\ &= \frac{q}{4\pi} \sin \theta d\theta \wedge d\phi. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\star F$ is not exact since the angle function ϕ is not continuous on S^1 .

For any 3-ball $B_r^3 \subset \tilde{M}$ of radius $r > 0$, center $\beta(t)$, and orthogonal to e_t , we have

$$(4) \quad \int_{\phi(\partial B_r^3)} \star F = \frac{q}{4\pi r^2} \int_{S_r^2} r^2 \sin \theta d\theta d\phi = q.$$

Stokes' theorem is not applicable in (4) since smooth n -forms see $\phi(\beta)$ as a hole in M , and thus $\phi(B^3)$ as non-compact. Whence, $\int_{\phi(\partial B_r^3)} \star F$ need not equal $\int_{\phi(B_r^3)} d\star F = 0$. Finally, observe that the dual F of $-\star F$ is closed,

$$F = -\frac{q}{4\pi r^2} dr \wedge dt = -\frac{q}{4\pi r^3} (x dx \wedge dt + y dy \wedge dt + z dz \wedge dt) = -d\left(\frac{q}{4\pi r} dt\right).$$

2.3. Interlude: harmonic forms on spacetime. We briefly recall some basic definitions in differential topology.

Let ω_1, ω_2 be square-integrable smooth n -forms on M . Consider their global inner product

$$(\omega_1, \omega_2) := \int_M \omega_1 \wedge \star \omega_2.$$

The *codifferential* $d^* : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega^{n-1}$ is the adjoint of the exterior derivative $d : \Omega^{n-1} \rightarrow \Omega^n$ with respect to (\cdot, \cdot) : for $\omega_1 \in \Omega^{n-1}$ and $\omega_2 \in \Omega^n$,

$$(d\omega_1, \omega_2) = (\omega_1, d^*\omega_2).$$

On a 4-dimensional Lorentzian manifold, $d^* = \star d \star$ [F2, (14.12)]. The same identity holds on an internal spacetime:

Lemma 2.9. *On an internal spacetime, we have $d^* = \star d \star$.*

Proof. Fix $n \in [1, 4]$. For $\omega \in \Omega^n$, $\star \star \omega = (-1)^{n(4-n)+1} \omega = (-1)^{n-1} \omega$. Thus, for $\omega_1 \in \Omega^{n-1}$ and $\omega_2 \in \Omega^n$,

$$\begin{aligned} (d\omega_1, \omega_2) - (\omega_1, \star d \star \omega_2) &= \int_M (d\omega_1 \wedge \star \omega_2 - \omega_1 \wedge \star (\star d \star \omega_2)) \\ &= \int_M (d\omega_1 \wedge \star \omega_2 - (-1)^{(4-n+1)-1} \omega_1 \wedge d \star \omega_2) \\ &= \int_M d(\omega_1 \wedge \star \omega_2) = \int_{\partial M} \omega_1 \wedge \star \omega_2 = \int_{\beta \in \mathcal{D}} \omega_1 \wedge \star \omega_2 = 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality holds because any tangent 1-form to a degenerate worldvolume $\beta \in \mathcal{D}$ vanishes identically. It follows that $(\omega_1, \star d \star \omega_2) = (\omega_1, d^* \omega_2)$. Since ω_1 and ω_2 are arbitrary, $d^* = \star d \star$. \square

A form ω is said to be *coclosed* if $d^* \omega = 0$; *coexact* if $\omega = d^* \eta$ for some η ; and *harmonic* if it is both closed and coclosed, $d\omega = d^* \omega = 0$. The space of harmonic n -forms on M is denoted $\mathcal{H}^n(M)$.

2.4. The electromagnetic field from spacetime topology. On a spacetime manifold \tilde{M} with charged particles, *an electromagnetic 2-form F can never be harmonic since $d^* F \neq 0$* . The situation is quite different on an internal spacetime M :

Definition 2.10. An *electromagnetic field* on M is a harmonic 2-form $\star F \in \mathcal{H}^2(M)$ such that for any spatial 3-ball $B^3 \subset \tilde{M}$,

$$(5) \quad \int_{\phi(\partial B^3)} \star F = \sum_{\beta(t) \in B^3} q_\beta,$$

where q_β is the electric charge of β .

Since $\star F$ is harmonic, whence closed, (5) implies that $\star F$ has nontrivial class in $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$. Consequently, *(the class of) $\star F$ is a topological invariant of spacetime M .*

Lemma 2.11. *The dual 2-form $F = -\star(\star F)$ has trivial class in $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$: there is a 1-form A for which $F = dA$.*

Proof. Since $\star F$ is harmonic, it is coclosed, and so F is closed. Thus, F is in $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$.

It suffices to suppose that there is only one pointal particle $\beta(t)$. By (5), $\star F$ is nontrivial in $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$. By Theorem 2.8, $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M) = H_{\text{dR}}^2(\tilde{M}\setminus\beta) \cong \mathbb{R}$ is 1-dimensional. Consequently, every class in $H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$ is a scalar multiple of the class $[\star F]$. Therefore, $[F] = 0 \in H_{\text{dR}}^2(M)$ since $[\star F]$ is not a scalar multiple of $[F]$. \square

Now fix normal coordinates $\{x_0 = t, x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ about a point in \tilde{M} . Given a spacelike vector u^a orthogonal to e_t , write $u^a = \sum_{i=1}^3 u^i e_i$, $u_a = \sum_{i=1}^3 u_i dx^i$, and set

$$u_{ab} := \star(u_a \wedge dt) = \sqrt{|\tilde{g}|} (u_1 dx^2 \wedge dx^3 + u_2 dx^3 \wedge dx^1 + u_3 dx^1 \wedge dx^2).$$

The electric and magnetic fields obtained from $\star F$ in the reference frame of e_t are

$$E_a := F_{ba} e_t^b \quad \text{and} \quad B_a := \star F_{ab} e_t^b.$$

Whence,

$$F_{ab} = E_a \wedge dt + B_{ab} \quad \text{and} \quad \star F_{ab} = E_{ab} - B_a \wedge dt.$$

Maxwell's equations then follow immediately from $dF = 0$ and (5). The integral (5) is in place of the usual Ampère-Gauss equation on \tilde{M} ,

$$d^*F = j_a,$$

where $j_a = \rho dt + \mathbf{j}_a$ is a current 1-form. To note, j_a is *not* a differential form on \tilde{M} , but rather a distribution-valued form, and vanishes on M .

The electromagnetic 2-form $\star F \in \mathcal{H}^2(M)$ in Definition 2.10 is not unique. Indeed, in contrast to compact Riemannian manifolds, nonzero forms on an internal spacetime can be both exact and coclosed. For example, the exact 2-form and its dual

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &= d(\omega^{-1} \sin(\omega(x-t)) dy) = \cos(\omega(x-t))(dx - dt) \wedge dy, \\ \star\psi &= \cos(\omega(x-t))(dx - dt) \wedge dz, \end{aligned}$$

are both closed. Furthermore, adding an exact form $\psi = d\alpha$ to $\star F$ does not affect the integral (5) since $\int_{S^2} \psi = \int_{\partial S^2} \alpha = \int_{\emptyset} \alpha = 0$:

$$\int_{\phi(\partial B^3)} (\star F + \psi) = \int_{\phi(\partial B^3)} \star F = \sum_{\beta(t) \in B^3} q_\beta.$$

We are therefore free to add exact harmonic forms to $\star F$. *These forms correspond to freely propagating electromagnetic waves.* Crucially, however, these waves are distinct from bound pairs of pointons—that is, *photons*. In the next section we will introduce a possible consequence of this distinction.

2.5. The Dirac equation from spacetime topology. In this section we use the signature $(+ - - -)$. To simplify notation, we assume $\tilde{M} = \mathbb{R}^{1,3}$ is Minkowski space.

We briefly review the well-known fact that harmonic forms satisfy a massless Dirac equation (e.g., [F2, 14.2]).

Set $\Omega := \bigoplus_{n \geq 0} \Omega^n$. The so-called Hodge-Dirac operator $\bar{\partial} := d + d^* : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega$ squares to the d'Alembertian $\partial^2 = \partial_t^2 - \nabla^2$,

$$\bar{\partial}^2 \omega = (dd^* + d^*d)\omega = \partial^2 \omega.$$

This operator is similar to the canonical Dirac operator $\not{\partial} := \gamma^j \partial_j$, since $\not{\partial}$ squares to ∂^2 on spinors $\psi \in \mathbb{C}^4$: $\not{\partial}^2 \psi = \partial^2 \psi$. Explicitly, $\bar{\partial}$ and $\not{\partial}$ can be related by setting

$$\bar{\gamma}(e_i) = \bar{\gamma}^i := dx^i \wedge + \iota_{e_i},$$

where for a vector $v \in T\tilde{M}$, the interior product $\iota_v : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega^{n-1}$ is given by the contraction $\iota_v \omega(u_1, \dots, u_{n-1}) = \omega(v, u_1, \dots, u_{n-1})$. Both the $\bar{\gamma}^i$ and gamma matrices $\gamma(e_i) := \gamma^i$ yield the same Clifford relations on \tilde{M} ,

$$\bar{\gamma}^i \bar{\gamma}^j + \bar{\gamma}^j \bar{\gamma}^i = 2\tilde{g}(e_i, e_j) = \gamma^i \gamma^j + \gamma^j \gamma^i.$$

The left-hand side holds since the relations $dx^i \wedge dx^j = -dx^j \wedge dx^i$ imply

$$\iota_{e_i} \iota_{e_j} = -\iota_{e_j} \iota_{e_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \iota_{e_i} dx^i + dx^i \iota_{e_i} = \tilde{g}(e_i, e_i).$$

Therefore, $\bar{\partial} = d + d^* = \bar{\gamma}^i \partial_i$.

By Definition 2.10, an electromagnetic 2-form $\star F$ on M is harmonic. Consequently, both $\star F$ and F satisfy the massless Dirac equation,

$$\bar{\partial} \star F = 0 = \bar{\partial} F.$$

Furthermore, recall that an exact harmonic 2-form $\psi \in \mathcal{H}^2(M)$ corresponds to an electromagnetic wave. Such forms then also satisfy the massless Dirac equation,

$$(6) \quad \bar{\partial} \psi = 0.$$

In our framework, photons are modeled by bound pairs of pointons. Electromagnetic waves $\psi \in \mathcal{H}^2(M)$ are thus free to exist independently of photons. The Dirac equation (6) then suggests the possibility that such waves act as single-particle pilot waves. More generally, (6) tentatively suggests that *exact harmonic n -forms $\psi \in \mathcal{H}^n(M)$ serve as pilot waves that model the observed quantum interference effects of individual particles.*

These massless waves, however, would propagate at the speed of light. They would therefore *not* be de Broglie-Bohm pilot waves. Furthermore, they would not be able to model wavefunctions of entangled particles, nor produce their spacelike correlations. Nevertheless, in Section 4 we will introduce a model of quantum entanglement based on the time dilation intrinsic to the geometry.

3. SPIN AND POLARIZATION FROM INTERNAL TANGENT SPACE GEOMETRY

In this section we present the conditional probabilities for spin and polarization that correspond to their wavefunction collapse, and show how the degenerate metric h gives rise to linear, circular, and elliptical polarization. Recall that in an internal spacetime, photons are modeled by bound pairs of pointons of opposite orientation.

3.1. Photon worldsheets. Consider a photon with null 4-velocity v . In order to define the metric h along its worldline, a null vector v' satisfying $v^a v'_a = -1$ must be chosen, by (1). Indeed, such a vector v' is necessary to obtain a minimal projection of v ,

$$(7) \quad [v]_{ab} := \tilde{g}_{ab} + v_a v'_b + v_b v'_a.$$

Observe that $[v]_{ab}$ also projects out v' : $[v]_{ab} v'^b = 0$. Furthermore, the condition $v^a v'_a = -1$ implies that v and v' are linearly independent. Therefore, *to project out a null vector, two dimensions must vanish*, namely, the span of v and v' . In particular, the photon's internal velocity is the 2-vector

$$\check{v} = \check{v}^{ab} = o \star (v \wedge v'),$$

for some choice of orientation $o \in \{\pm 1\}$. The tangent spaces along the worldline of a free photon are thus 2-dimensional. Consequently, a photon's worldline necessarily lies in a degenerate worldsheet in \mathcal{D} : photons have worldsheets rather than just worldlines.

3.2. Spin and polarization probabilities. Again consider a photon with null 4-velocity v . The spin vector s of the photon is the sum of the unit spin vectors s_+ , s_- of its constituent pointons,

$$(8) \quad s := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(s_+ - s_-).$$

These unit vectors are Fermi transported along the integral curves $\beta \subset \tilde{M}$ of v in the photon's worldsheet until the tangent space dimension changes.

At points $\beta(t) \in \tilde{M}$ along β where the photon propagates freely, $\dim M_{\beta(t)} = 2$. Thus, at these points, we may choose the decomposition (8) so that s_+ , s_- are orthogonal, $s_+^a s_{-a} = 0$. Given a unit vector u , it will be convenient to define

$$(9) \quad s \star u := (s_+ \cdot u)(s_- \cdot u) \stackrel{(1)}{=} \cos \vartheta \cos(\vartheta - \frac{\pi}{2}) = \cos \vartheta \sin \vartheta,$$

where in (1) ϑ is the angle between s_+ and u , and we are taking s_+ to be s_- rotated counterclockwise by $\pi/2$ in the plane $\text{span}\{s_+, s_-\} \subset \tilde{M}_p$.

Now consider a pointon (resp. photon) with worldline (resp. integral curve) $\beta \subset \tilde{M}$. Suppose that there is a point $p = \beta(t_0) \in \tilde{M}$ for which $\dim M_p = 1$, and an $\epsilon > 0$ such that for $t \in [t_0 - \epsilon, t_0) \cup (t_0, t_0 + \epsilon]$, $\dim M_{\beta(t)} > 1$ is constant. Fix a unit vector u in M_p . We define the following probability densities:

- $\rho(u|s)$ is the probability density that the particle's spin vector at p will be u , given that its spin vector at $\beta(t_0 - \epsilon)$ is s .
- $\rho(s|u)$ is the probability density that the particle's spin vector at $\beta(t_0 + \epsilon)$ will be s , given that its spin vector at p is u .

By (2), s transforms into or emerges from u at p only if

$$(10) \quad \begin{aligned} \hat{h}_p(s) &= u \quad \text{for pointons} \\ \hat{h}_p(s_+) &= \hat{h}_p(s_-) = u \quad \text{for photons} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, again by (2),

$$(11) \quad \begin{aligned} \rho(u|s) &:= \begin{cases} \mathbb{1}(s \cdot u) & \text{for pointons} \\ \mathbb{1}(s * u) & \text{for photons} \end{cases} \\ \rho(s|u) &:= \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\pi} s \cdot u \mathbb{1}(s \cdot u) & \text{for pointons} \\ s * u \mathbb{1}(s * u) & \text{for photons} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbb{1}$ is the Heaviside function, and the sample spaces are the set of unit vectors s in $M_{\beta(t_0 \pm \epsilon)} \cong \mathbb{R}^d$, that is, the unit sphere $S^{d-1} \subset M_{\beta(t_0 \pm \epsilon)}$. The normalizations π and 1 are shown in Lemmas 3.2 and 4.5 below.

The outcome of a measurement of s in the direction u at p , denoted $\bar{u}(s) \in \{0, \pm 1\}$, is determined by $\rho(u|s)$:

$$(12) \quad \bar{u}(s) := \begin{cases} \mathbb{1}(s \cdot u) - \mathbb{1}(-s \cdot u) & \text{for pointons} \\ \mathbb{1}(s * u) - \mathbb{1}(-s * u) & \text{for photons} \end{cases}$$

Consequently, the probability density that s will be the particle's spin vector after it emerges from $M_p = \text{span}\{u\}$ is

$$(13) \quad \rho(s|M_p) = \frac{1}{2} (\rho(s|\bar{u}(s) = 1) + \rho(s|\bar{u}(s) = -1)).$$

Lemma 3.1. *For pointons, $\bar{u}(s) = -\bar{u}(-s)$, whereas for photons,*

$$\bar{u}(s) = \bar{u}(-s) = -\bar{u}(s_\perp) = -\bar{u}(-s_\perp),$$

where s_\perp is orthogonal to s in $M_{\beta(t_0 - \epsilon)}$.

Proof. These relations are straightforward to verify using (12). □

The following shows that the probabilities (11) are similar to Born's rule for spin.

Lemma 3.2. *The probability that a spin vector prepared from v projects onto u is*

$$\mathbb{P}(u|v) = \int_{S^2} \rho(u|s) \rho(s|v) ds = (u \cdot v)^2.$$

Proof. It suffices to suppose $u \cdot v \geq 0$. Consider the orthonormal basis of $M_{\beta(t_0 \pm \epsilon)}$,

$$e_1 = u \times v, \quad e_2 = v \times e_1, \quad e_3 = v.$$

Let $\phi \in [0, 2\pi)$, $\theta \in [0, \pi]$ be such that $u = \cos \phi \sin \theta e_1 + \sin \phi \sin \theta e_2 + \cos \theta e_3$. Denote by $\mathbf{H}_u, \mathbf{H}_v \subset S^2$ the unit hemispheres defined by u and v . Then

$$(14) \quad \mathbf{H}_v := \{\cos \varphi \sin \vartheta e_1 + \sin \varphi \sin \vartheta e_2 + \cos \vartheta e_3 \mid \varphi \in [0, 2\pi), \vartheta \in [0, \frac{\pi}{2}]\}.$$

Furthermore, the intersection $\mathbf{H}_u \cap \mathbf{H}_v$ is twice the region parameterized by $\varphi \in [0, \pi]$ and $\vartheta \in [\theta, \frac{\pi}{2}]$. Thus, by (11),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}(u|v) &= \int_{S^2} \rho(u|s) \rho(s|v) ds = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{S^2} \mathbf{1}(s \cdot u) (s \cdot v) \mathbf{1}(s \cdot v) ds \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\mathbf{H}_u \cap \mathbf{H}_v} s \cdot v ds = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_{\theta}^{\pi/2} \int_0^{\pi} \cos \vartheta \sin \vartheta d\varphi d\vartheta = \frac{2}{2} \sin^2 \vartheta \Big|_{\theta}^{\pi/2} = \cos^2 \theta. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, $\mathbf{P}(u|u) = 1$, and so $1/\pi$ is the normalization constant of $\rho(s|v)$. \square

3.3. Linear, circular, and elliptical polarization. Again consider a photon with null 4-velocity v . The polarization of the photon—linear, circular, or elliptical—results from the choice of v' in (7), and thus the metric h . Specifically, $\{v, v', s_+, s_-\}$ is a basis for $\tilde{M}_{\beta(t)}$ with kernel and image bases

$$\text{span}\{v, v'\} = \ker h_a^b = M_{\beta(t)}^{\perp}, \quad \text{span}\{s_+, s_-\} = \text{im } h_a^b = M_{\beta(t)}.$$

Let e_0, e_1, e_2, e_3 be an orthonormal tetrad for which $v = e_0 + e_3$, Fermi transported along the integral curves of v in the worldsheet of the photon. Using (11), we identify the polarization of the photon to be⁴

- linear in the direction s if $v' = \frac{1}{2}(e_0 - e_3)$;
- circular if $v' = e_0 + w$ for some unit vector $w \in \text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$; and
- elliptical otherwise.

Observe that in the linear case, s lies in the plane orthogonal to the photons direction of motion, namely $\text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$.

For circular polarization with $v' = e_0 + w$, let $w_{\perp} \in \text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$ be an orthogonal vector to w . Then $M_{\beta(t)}$ has orthonormal basis

$$s_+ = \pm(v + w) = \pm(-e_0 + v + v'), \quad s_- = w_{\perp}.$$

Furthermore, $s_+ = v + w$ and $s_+ = -(v + w)$ yield orthogonal circular polarizations, by (11). In a forthcoming paper we describe how the 2-dimensional tangent space of a photon continuously twists along its worldline as it passes through a waveplate, swiveling the tangent space between linear and circular polarizations.

⁴We have modified our choice of v' corresponding to circular polarization from that given in [B5, (16)] in order to remove the null constraint in [B5, Corollary 6.6].

4. A DERIVATION OF THE BELL STATE CORRELATIONS AND MALUS'S LAW

4.1. Bell state entanglement in internal spacetime. In the following, we introduce a geometric model of the Bell states

$$(15) \quad |\Phi^\pm\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\uparrow\rangle \pm |\downarrow\downarrow\rangle), \quad |\Psi^\pm\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow\downarrow\rangle \pm |\downarrow\uparrow\rangle).$$

Recall that pointons only interact by pair creation and annihilation of opposite charge (i.e., orientation). This simple interaction then yields electron-photon trivalent vertices, shown in Figure 1; see also [B1].

Definition 4.1. We call a union of pointon worldlines $\beta = \beta_1 \cup \beta_2 \cup \dots \cup \beta_n$ a *pointon line* if each consecutive pair β_i, β_{i+1} is joined by pointon creation or annihilation. In particular, β_i and β_{i+1} share a common endpoint in \tilde{M} .

Since β_i and β_{i+1} are each single points in M , they are coincident (though distinct) points in M . It follows that β is a union of n coincident points in M , in stark contrast to its appearance in \tilde{M} .

Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \subset \tilde{M}$ be segments of the worldlines of two pointons that start at a common point $p \in \tilde{M}$ and end respectively at points $q_1, q_2 \in \tilde{M}$. Furthermore, suppose that $\dim M_{q_1} = \dim M_{q_2} = 1$. Fix unit vectors

$$a \in M_{q_1} \quad \text{and} \quad b \in M_{q_2}.$$

Definition 4.2. We call two electrons (resp. photons) a *Bell state* if their spin vectors s_1, s_2 satisfy $s_2 = \pm s_1$ (resp. $s_1 \cdot s_2 = 0$) at p , and there is a pointon line $\beta \subset \tilde{M}$ from p to q_1 (or q_2) such that the Fermi transport of a (or b) lies in each subspace $M_{\beta(t)}$.

Figure 1.i shows two photons in a Bell state, where β is the pointon line drawn in purple, and p is either trivalent vertex, p_1 or p_2 . Similarly, Figure 1.ii shows two electrons in a Bell state, where β is the pointon line drawn in purple (resp. either purple or blue) if $p = p_1$ (resp. $p = p_2$). We note that, contrary to its appearance in \tilde{M} , p_1 is *not* in the past of p_2 : they belong to a single pointon line, and so the vertices are simultaneous events in M . Similarly, q_1 is *not* in the future of p_1 , since again they are simultaneous events in M . A pointon line is thus a *line of simultaneity*.

4.2. Measurement independence from metric degeneracy. The degenerate geometry of internal spacetime is constructed from our proposal that time is stationary along a set of worldlines. As a result, these worldlines exhibit a new form of time dilation; see Figure 2.i. In the context of a Bell state, *it is precisely this time dilation that yields the illusion of measurement dependence*. This suggests that, in general, *nonlocal quantum phenomena arise because time dilation can occur within a single inertial frame*.

In a hidden variable model, the set of hidden variables λ are free to depend on the preparation procedure P ,

$$\rho(\lambda|P) \neq \rho(\lambda).$$

FIGURE 2. (i) Internal time dilation. (ii) The worldline α_1 is a (union of coincident) single point(s) in spacetime M , and so its endpoints p , q_1 are coincident. Furthermore, the Fermi transport of M_{q_1} along α_1 lies in M_p . Thus, the Bell state is prepared at q_1 and measured at q_2 .

In contrast, the model is said to possess measurement (or statistical) independence if λ does not depend on the detector settings D ,

$$(16) \quad \rho(\lambda | D) = \rho(\lambda).$$

Failure of this property is usually regarded as untenable; see for example [G-Z].

Proposition 4.3. *The probability densities $\rho(s | M_{q_i})$ in (13) do not violate measurement independence in spacetime M , although they do in \tilde{M} .*

Proof. Referring to Figure 2.ii, consider a Bell state prepared at p and measured at q_1 , q_2 in \tilde{M} . Suppose that there is a pointon line $\beta = \alpha_1 \subset \tilde{M}$ connecting p to q_1 . (In Figure 1.i, there is a pointon line from $p \in \{p_1, p_2\}$ to both q_1 and q_2 , drawn in purple. In Figure 1.ii, there is a pointon line from $p \in \{p_1, p_2\}$ to q_1 in purple, and to q_2 in blue.) Since β is a union of coincident points in M , its endpoints $p, q_2 \in \tilde{M}$ are also coincident points in M .

By assumption, each tangent space $M_{\beta(t)}$ along β contains the Fermi transport of $M_{q_1} = \text{span}\{a\}$. Hence, M_{q_1} can be Fermi transported along β to M_p without encountering any projections. Thus, the Fermi transport $M_{q_1 \rightarrow p}$ of M_{q_1} to p is a subspace of M_p . It follows that the preparation of s at p is equivalent to its preparation at q_1 , and s is prepared from $M_{q_1 \rightarrow p} \subseteq M_p$. Therefore, we may take s to be prepared at q_1 and measured at q_2 , that is, $P = M_{q_1}$ and $D = M_{q_2}$. But then

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(s | P) &= \rho(s | M_{q_1}) \neq \rho(s), \\ \rho(s | D) &= \rho(s | M_{q_2}) = \rho(s). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, (16) is satisfied and our model has measurement independence in M . \square

FIGURE 3. Preparation and measurement of parallel spin vectors $s_1 = s_2 =: s$, shown together on the right. The product of the measurement outcomes $\bar{a}(s)\bar{b}(s)$ is given by the \pm signs around the circle.

We remark that, by (11), our model is not deterministic, and thus not superdeterministic. In an internal spacetime, the illusion of measurement dependence is simply the result of time dilation.

4.3. Correlations of entangled electrons. In this section we derive the Bell state expectation values for electrons, modeled as pointons.

Consider two pointons in a Bell state, prepared at p and measured at q_1, q_2 in \tilde{M} , and prepared at q_1 and measured at q_2 in spacetime M . Let s_1, s_2 be the unit spin vectors of the pointons; then $s := s_1 = \pm s_2$. Suppose the detector settings at $q_1, q_2 \in \tilde{M}$ are the unit vectors a, b respectively. That is, the spin vectors s_1, s_2 meet 1-dimensional tangent spaces at q_1, q_2 :

$$M_{q_1} = \text{span}\{a\}, \quad M_{q_2} = \text{span}\{b\}.$$

Then by (12),

$$\bar{a}(s) = \mathbb{1}(s \cdot a) - \mathbb{1}(-s \cdot a), \quad \bar{b}(s) = \mathbb{1}(s \cdot b) - \mathbb{1}(-s \cdot b).$$

Thus, (13) implies

$$\rho(s|P) = \rho(s|M_{q_1}) = \frac{1}{2}(\rho(s|a) + \rho(s|-a)).$$

With these in hand, the expected value of the product $\bar{a}\bar{b}$ is simply

$$\langle \bar{a}\bar{b} \rangle_{\pm} := \int_{S^2} \rho(s|P) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(\pm s) ds = \int_{S^2} \rho(s|M_{q_1}) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(\pm s) ds.$$

Theorem 4.4. *Two pointons (i.e., electrons) in a Bell state have correlation*

$$\langle \bar{a}\bar{b} \rangle_{\pm} = \pm a \cdot b.$$

Proof. It suffices to suppose that $s_1 = s_2 =: s$ since $\bar{b}(-s) = -\bar{b}(s)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \bar{a}\bar{b} \rangle_+ &= \int_{S^2} \rho(s | M_{q_1}) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(s) ds \stackrel{(i)}{=} \int_{S^2} \frac{1}{2} (\rho(s | a) + \rho(s | -a)) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(s) ds \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{S^2} s \cdot a (\mathbf{1}(s \cdot a) - \mathbf{1}(-s \cdot a)) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(s) ds \\
 (17) \quad &\stackrel{(ii)}{=} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{S^2} s \cdot a (\bar{a}(s))^2 \bar{b}(s) ds \stackrel{(iii)}{=} \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\int_{s \cdot b > 0} - \int_{s \cdot b < 0} \right) s \cdot a ds,
 \end{aligned}$$

where (i) holds by (13); and (ii) and (iii) hold by (3). Using the hemisphere parameterization (14) with $v = e_3 = b$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_{\mathbb{H}_b} s \cdot a ds &= \int_0^{\pi/2} \int_0^{2\pi} (\cos \varphi \sin \vartheta e_1 + \sin \varphi \sin \vartheta e_2 + \cos \vartheta e_3) \cdot a \sin \vartheta d\varphi d\vartheta \\
 &= \int_0^{\pi/2} (\sin \varphi|_0^{2\pi} \sin \vartheta e_1 - \cos \varphi|_0^{2\pi} \sin \vartheta e_2 + 2\pi \cos \vartheta b) \cdot a \sin \vartheta d\vartheta = \pi a \cdot b.
 \end{aligned}$$

It therefore follows from (17) that

$$\langle \bar{a}\bar{b} \rangle_+ = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\int_{\mathbb{H}_b} - \int_{\mathbb{H}_{-b}} \right) s \cdot a ds = \frac{\pi}{2\pi} a \cdot b - \frac{\pi}{2\pi} a \cdot (-b) = a \cdot b.$$

□

Recall the Clauser-Horne-Shimony-Holt inequality [Be, CHSH],

$$|\langle \bar{a}_0 \bar{b}_0 \rangle + \langle \bar{a}_0 \bar{b}_1 \rangle + \langle \bar{a}_1 \bar{b}_0 \rangle - \langle \bar{a}_1 \bar{b}_1 \rangle| \leq 2.$$

Our model violates this inequality for certain choices of tangent spaces a_0, a_1, b_0, b_1 , just as in quantum theory; for example,

$$a_0 = e_2, \quad a_1 = e_1, \quad b_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(e_1 + e_2), \quad b_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(e_1 - e_2).$$

These violations have been confirmed by experiment (e.g., [ADR, FC, P-Z]). However, although our model is nonlocal in space, *it is local in spacetime M*.

4.4. Malus's law and correlations of entangled photons. In this section we derive Malus's law and the Bell state expectation values for photons, modeled as bound pairs of pointons.

Throughout, consider a photon with null 4-velocity v and linear polarization s . Choose an orthonormal tetrad e_0, e_1, e_2, e_3 for which $v = e_0 + e_3$, Fermi transported along the integral curves of v in the worldsheet of the photon. Then, since the polarization is linear, s is in $\text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$. Recall that the tangent spaces along the photon's worldsheet are at most 2-dimensional by (7), and $s = s_+ - s_-$ is the sum of the spin vectors of its constituent two pointons. It suffices to suppose that s_+ is s_- rotated counterclockwise by $\pi/2$.

Suppose there is a 1-dimensional tangent space $M_q \subset \tilde{M}_q$ at $q \in \tilde{M}$ spanned by a spacelike unit vector u . By (10) and (11), the probability densities for the absorption and transmission of the photon at q are respectively

$$(18) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{absorbed:} & \text{transmitted:} \\ \rho_a(u|s) := \rho(u|s) = \mathbb{1}(s*u) & \rho_t(u|s) := \mathbb{1}(-s*u) \\ \rho_a(s|u) := \rho(s|u) = s*u \mathbb{1}(s*u) & \rho_t(s|u) := -s*u \mathbb{1}(-s*u) \end{array}$$

Lemma 4.5. *The photon probability densities (18) are normalized.*

Proof. Choose e_1, e_2 so that $e_1 = u$. Write $s_+ = \cos \vartheta e_1 + \sin \vartheta e_2$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} P(u|u) &= \int_{S^1} \rho(u|s)\rho(s|u)ds = \int_{S^1} s*u (\mathbb{1}(s*u))^2 ds \\ &\stackrel{(i)}{=} \left(\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} + \int_{\pi}^{\frac{3\pi}{2}} \right) \cos \vartheta \sin \vartheta d\vartheta = -\frac{1}{2} \cos^2 \vartheta \Big|_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} - \frac{1}{2} \cos^2 \vartheta \Big|_{\pi}^{\frac{3\pi}{2}} = 1, \end{aligned}$$

where (i) holds by (9). \square

Now suppose the photon meets two linear polarizers, with consecutive polarization directions $u_1, u_2 \in \text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$. The probability of transmission through both linear polarizers is thus

$$P_t(u_2|u_1) = \int_{S^1} \rho_t(u_2|s)\rho_t(s|u_1) ds.$$

Remark 4.6. A linear polarizer in the direction $u \in \text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$ can be realized by an electron whose 3-velocity is (approximately) confined to the direction $u_{\perp} = u \times e_3 \in \text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$, such as in a wire or a stretched molecule, since the electron's 4-velocity vanishes on M [B5, §7]. In particular, u_{\perp} vanishes in the tangent space M_q at any point $q \in \tilde{M}$ where the photon and electron meet: $M_q = \text{span}\{u\}$.

Theorem 4.7. *A photon with linear polarization satisfies Malus's law,*

$$P_t(u_2|u_1) = (u_1 \cdot u_2)^2 = \cos^2 \theta,$$

where θ is the angle between u_1 and u_2 .

Proof. Choose e_1, e_2 so that $e_1 = u_1$. Write

$$u := u_2 = \cos \theta e_1 + \sin \theta e_2 \quad \text{and} \quad -s_- = \cos \vartheta e_1 + \sin \vartheta e_2.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} P_t(u|e_1) &= \int_{S^1} \rho_t(u|s)\rho_t(s|e_1) ds \stackrel{(i)}{=} \int_{S^1} \mathbb{1}(-s*u) (-s*e_1) \mathbb{1}(-s*e_1) ds \\ &\stackrel{(ii)}{=} \left(\int_{\theta}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} + \int_{\pi+\theta}^{\frac{3\pi}{2}} \right) \sin \vartheta \cos \vartheta d\vartheta = -\frac{1}{2} \cos^2 \vartheta \Big|_{\theta}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} + -\frac{1}{2} \cos^2 \vartheta \Big|_{\pi+\theta}^{\frac{3\pi}{2}} = \cos^2 \theta, \end{aligned}$$

where (I) holds by (18) and (II) holds by (9):

$$s * e_1 = (s_+ \cdot e_1)(s_- \cdot e_1) = \cos(\vartheta + \frac{\pi}{2}) \cos \vartheta = -\sin \vartheta \cos \vartheta.$$

□

Finally, consider two photons in a Bell state, prepared at p and measured at q_1, q_2 in \tilde{M} , and prepared at q_1 and measured at q_2 in spacetime M . Let s_1, s_2 be the spin vectors of the photons; then $s := s_1 \in \{s_2, s_{2\perp}\}_2$ up to sign, by Lemma 3.1. Let a, b be the unit vector detector settings at $q_1, q_2 \in \tilde{M}$ respectively. By (12),

$$(19) \quad \bar{a}(s) = \mathbb{1}(s * a) - \mathbb{1}(-s * a), \quad \bar{b}(s) = \mathbb{1}(s * b) - \mathbb{1}(-s * b).$$

Thus, since $M_{q_1} = \text{span}\{a\}$, (13) and (18) together imply

$$(20) \quad \rho(s|P) = \rho(s|M_{q_1}) = \frac{1}{2}(\rho(s|a) + \rho(s|a_\perp)) = \frac{1}{2}(\rho_a(s|a) + \rho_t(s|a)).$$

Since we are assuming that the Bell state is prepared at $q_1 \in M$, the Fermi transport of a along α_1 lies in each tangent space $M_{\alpha_1(t)}$. In the following, we similarly suppose that the Fermi transport of b along α_2 lies in each tangent space $M_{\alpha_2(t)}$.

Theorem 4.8. *Two photons with linear polarization in a Bell state have correlation*

$$\langle \bar{a}\bar{b} \rangle_\pm = \pm \cos(2\theta),$$

where θ is the angle between a and b .

Proof. Choose e_1, e_2 so that $e_1 = a$. Write

$$b = \cos \theta e_1 + \sin \theta e_2 \quad \text{and} \quad s_+ = \cos \vartheta e_1 + \sin \vartheta e_2.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \bar{a}\bar{b} \rangle_+ &= \int_{S^1} \rho(s|M_{q_1}) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(s) ds \stackrel{(i)}{=} \int_{S^1} \frac{1}{2}(\rho_a(s|a) + \rho_t(s|a)) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(s) ds \\ &\stackrel{(ii)}{=} \frac{1}{2} \int_{S^1} s * a (\mathbb{1}(s * a) - \mathbb{1}(-s * a)) \bar{a}(s) \bar{b}(s) ds \\ &\stackrel{(iii)}{=} \frac{1}{2} \int_{S^1} s * a (\bar{a}(s))^2 \bar{b}(s) ds \stackrel{(iv)}{=} \frac{1}{2} \int_{S^1} s * a (\mathbb{1}(s * b) - \mathbb{1}(-s * b)) ds \\ &\stackrel{(v)}{=} \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_\theta^{\frac{\pi}{2}+\theta} - \int_{\frac{\pi}{2}+\theta}^{\pi+\theta} + \int_{\pi+\theta}^{\frac{3\pi}{2}+\theta} - \int_{\frac{3\pi}{2}+\theta}^\theta \right) \cos \vartheta \sin \vartheta d\vartheta \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{4}{2} (\sin^2 \theta - \cos^2 \theta) = \cos(2\theta), \end{aligned}$$

where (i) holds by (20); (ii) holds by (18); (iii) and (iv) hold by (19); and (v) holds by (9). □

4.5. Tangent space arrangements for the Bell states. In the following, we take \tilde{M} to be Minkowski space $\mathbb{R}^{1,3}$.

In determining the probabilities (11), only the angles between vectors are relevant by (10), and so it simplifies notation to assume that spin vectors are unit vectors. In this section we omit this normalization condition.

Fix an orthonormal basis e_1, e_2, e_3 of \mathbb{R}^3 . Recall the Pauli matrices

$$\sigma_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix},$$

and the associated \mathbb{R} -linear map $\sigma : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow i\mathfrak{su}(2)$ given by $e_j \mapsto \sigma_j$. Denote by $\mathcal{H} \cong \mathbb{C}^2$ the Hilbert space upon which the σ_j act. Set $|\uparrow\rangle := \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$, $|\downarrow\rangle := \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathcal{H}$, and consider the orthonormal tensor product basis $|\alpha\beta\rangle := |\alpha\rangle \otimes |\beta\rangle \in \mathcal{H} \otimes_{\mathbb{C}} \mathcal{H}$ where $\alpha, \beta \in \{\uparrow, \downarrow\}$. The Bell states are then given by (15), and their expectation values are

$$\begin{aligned} \langle ab \rangle_{\Phi^\pm} &:= \langle \Phi^\pm | \sigma(a) \otimes \sigma(b) | \Phi^\pm \rangle = \pm(a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2) + a_3 b_3, \\ \langle ab \rangle_{\Psi^\pm} &:= \langle \Psi^\pm | \sigma(a) \otimes \sigma(b) | \Psi^\pm \rangle = \pm(a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2) - a_3 b_3. \end{aligned}$$

As is well known, it follows that $|\Psi^-\rangle$ has total spin 0 (a singlet state), and $|\Phi^-\rangle$, $|\Phi^+\rangle$, $|\Psi^+\rangle$ each have total spin 1 (triplet states), with conserved total spin angular momentum in the e_1, e_2, e_3 directions respectively.

Now consider two particles in a Bell state with spin vectors s_1, s_2 in an internal spacetime M . Suppose the state is prepared at an electron-photon vertex $p \in \tilde{M}$ in a scattering diagram, as in Figures 1.i and 1.ii. Further suppose that $\dim M_p = 2$, and the tangent space M_{p_i} at each electron-photon vertex $p_i \in \tilde{M}$ in the diagram is the Fermi transport of M_p along the pointon line.

Analogous to spin angular momentum conservation, we propose that at each interaction vertex p_i , the incoming and outgoing spin vectors satisfy

$$\sum_{s \text{ in}} h_{p_i}(s) = \sum_{s' \text{ out}} h_{p_i}(s'),$$

where $h_{p_i}(s) := h_a^b s^a$ is the projection of s onto M_{p_i} . Summing over all the incoming and outgoing external legs of the diagram, set

$$s_0 := \sum_{s \text{ external in}} s - \sum_{\substack{s' \text{ external out,} \\ s' \notin \{s_1, s_2\}}} s'.$$

The tangent spaces that reproduce $|\Psi^\pm\rangle$ and $|\Phi^\pm\rangle$ are then:

s_0	\Rightarrow total spin	$h_p(s_0)$	if $s_0 \propto e_3$ and	\Rightarrow quantum state
$= 0$	0	$= 0$	M_p any plane	$ \Psi^-\rangle$
$\neq 0$	1	$= 0$	$M_p = \text{span}\{e_1, e_2\}$	$ \Psi^+\rangle$
		$\neq 0$	$M_p = \text{span}\{e_2, e_3\}$	$ \Phi^-\rangle$
		$\neq 0$	$M_p = \text{span}\{e_1, e_3\}$	$ \Phi^+\rangle$

4.6. A model of entanglement swapping. In entanglement swapping, two pairs of entangled particles, 1, 2 and 3, 4, are prepared in the state $|\Psi^-\rangle$ [H-Z]. Photons 2 and 3 then travel to a 50/50 beam splitter, interfere, and become entangled from a Bell state measurement. This measurement causes particles 1 and 4 to become entangled, and disentangles the pairs 1, 2 and 3, 4. The wavefunction of the four particles is

$$|\Psi^-\rangle_{12} \otimes |\Psi^-\rangle_{34} = \frac{1}{2} (|\Psi^+\rangle_{14} \otimes |\Psi^+\rangle_{23} - |\Psi^-\rangle_{14} \otimes |\Psi^-\rangle_{23} - |\Phi^+\rangle_{14} \otimes |\Phi^+\rangle_{23} + |\Phi^-\rangle_{14} \otimes |\Phi^-\rangle_{23}),$$

where the state is represented in the initial physical basis on the left, and in the final physical basis on the right.

In Figure 4 (left) we show that entanglement swapping with four photons can be modeled using pointon worldlines. In the diagram, γ_1, γ_4 are entangled from the pointon line drawn in red, and γ_5, γ_6 are entangled from the pointon line drawn in orange.

If a mirror is used instead of a beam splitter, then the pair 2, 3 undergoes a separable state measurement. Consequently, pairs 1, 2 and 3, 4 continue to be separately entangled. The diagram for this scenario is given in Figure 4 (right), where γ_1, γ_5 are entangled from the red pointon line; and γ_4, γ_6 are entangled from the orange pointon line.

Since there is no dependence on the location of the beam splitter, the choice of beam splitter or mirror could be made *after* particles 1 and 4 have been measured. This delayed choice scenario, proposed by Peres [P], has been confirmed by experiment [M-Z]. The internal spacetime diagram for this scenario is fundamentally the same as entanglement swapping without delayed choice, since time is stationary along pointon worldlines.

Acknowledgments: The author was supported by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) grant P 34854.

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FIGURE 4. Left: Entanglement swapping, with photons γ_1, γ_2 entangled in the beam splitter (BS) at q . Here, γ_1, γ_4 are entangled from the red pointon line, and γ_5, γ_6 from the orange pointon line. Right: The beam splitter is replaced by a mirror (M) at q . In this case, γ_1, γ_5 are entangled from the red line, and γ_4, γ_6 from the orange line.

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